

Search for Potential Antitumour Compounds. Part IV. Synthesis of Some Analogues of Folic Acid

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Analogues of folic acid, in which the pteridine ring is replaced by pyridoxine, have been synthesised with a view to testing their antitumour activity.

After demonstration of the usefulness of analogues of folic acid (I) in the treatment of acute leukemia in children¹, several analogues of folic acid have been prepared and tested with the hope of finding among them a more specific and less toxic agent. Several compounds in which the pteridine ring of folic acid has been replaced by other ring systems, e.g. benzimidazole², quinazoline³ etc., show definite antifolic activity. As no reports of replacing the pteridine ring by other growth factors have appeared in the literature, attempt is being made to synthesise a number of analogues of folic acid of type (II), in which the pteridine ring is replaced by a pyridoxine nucleus, specially when several derivatives of pyridoxine display a weak inhibitory activity on the growth of sarcoma 180 in mice⁴ and inhibit the growth of malignant cells in tissue culture⁵.

The analogues of folic acid were synthesised as shown in Chart I

The phenolic and 4-hydroxymethyl groups of pyridoxine hydrochloride were protected by converting it to isopropylidene-pyridoxine which was subsequently converted to its chloro derivative (III) according to the method of Cohen and Hughes⁶. Condensation of this compound (III) with ethyl *para*-aminobenzoate and subsequent hydrolysis of the resulting ester furnished 5-(*p*-carboxyphenyl) aminomethyl-3-hydroxy-4-hydroxymethyl-2-

1. Farber *et al.*, *Engl. J. Med.*, 1948, 239, 787.
2. Edward *et al.*, *Science*, 1948 107, 119.
3. Wooley and Pringle, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, 174, 327.
4. Wiley and Irick, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, 5, 49.
5. Testa *et al.*, *Chimia (Aarau)*, 1961, 15, 314.
6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4384.

methylpyridine (IV). Different amino-acids were then condensed with the free carboxyl group, using, *NN'*-dicyclohexylcarbodi-imide as the condensing agent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Amino-acid esters were prepared according to the method of Kupryozewski *et al.* Pyridoxine hydrochloride was first converted to isopropylidene pyridoxine by passing dry HCl gas into its suspension in dry acetone. The hydroxyl group at position-5 was then replaced by chloro group, using thionyl chloride, giving rise to 5-chloromethyl-3-hydroxy-4-hydroxymethyl-2-methylpyridine isopropylidene derivative (III)⁶.

4-[(2-Methyl-3-hydroxy-4-hydroxymethyl-5-pyridil)methyl]amino benzoic Acid (IV).—A mixture of the 5-chloromethyl compound (III) (0.05M), ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (0.05M), anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.), and anhydrous ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was then cooled in ice and filtered. Concentration of the filtrate to half its volume provided an ester on cooling. It was recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol, m.p. 120-21°, yield 72%. (Found: N, 8.8. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.9%).

The ester (0.04M) obtained above was refluxed with 5*N*-ethanolic NaOH (100 ml) for 4 hr. The ethanol was then removed and the residue dissolved in water. The aqueous solution was made acidic with acetic acid when the required acid (IV) separated. It was

recrystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 250° (decomp.), yield 69%. (Found: N, 9.5. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.7%).

N-[4-(2-Methyl-3-hydroxy-4-hydroxymethyl-5-pyridil)methyl]amino-benzoyl-amino-acid (II).—A mixture of the acid (0.005M), obtained above, the appropriate amino-acid ester (0.005M), *NN'*-dicyclohexylcarbodi-imide (0.01M), and methylene chloride was shaken for 4 hr. The solid separating was filtered and the filtrate washed at first with dilute acid and then with aqueous sodium bicarbonate. On removing the methylene chloride from the filtrate, the ester of the desired compound was obtained. The yield, m.p., and analyses of the esters obtained by this method are recorded in Table I.

*TABLE I

Amino-acid.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		
				Found.	Reqd.				Found.	Reqd.	
A. —R ₁ = Et				B. —R ₁ = H							
Glycine	86°	66	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃	11.2	11.3	129°	57	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₃	12.0	12.2	
Alanine	101°	60	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₃	11.0	10.9	176°	49	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃	11.6	11.7	
α-Amino-n-butyrac acid	173°	57	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₃	10.2	10.5	209°	52	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃	11.0	11.2	
α-Amino-iso-butyrac acid	127°	48	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₃	10.4	10.5	189°	67	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃	11.0	11.2	
Valine	166°	39	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ O ₅ N ₃	9.9	10.1	178°	73	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₃	11.0	11.9	
Leucine	109°	67	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ O ₅ N ₃	9.7	9.8	198°	50	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₃	10.4	10.5	
Isoleucine	189°	63	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ O ₅ N ₃	9.5	9.8	204°	57	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₃	10.3	10.5	
Tyrosine	216°	52	C ₂₆ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₃	8.7	8.8	> 250°	61	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₃	9.2	9.3	
Glutamic acid	96°	46	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ O ₇ N ₃	8.6	8.9	119°	46	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₃	9.2	9.4	
Phenylglycine	117°	53	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₃	9.3	9.4	196°	50	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₃	10.1	9.9	

*Vide structure (II).

The esters obtained above were saponified (boiling water bath) with acetone-N-NaOH (about 15-20% excess of NaOH) for about ½ hr. After addition of a slight excess of N-acetic acid, the mixture was concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue obtained was recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol. The yield, m.p., and analyses of the folic acid analogues are reported in Table I.

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